

Achieving Quality and Efficiency of Education is the Main Goal of the State National Education System

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Abstract: In this article, in the years of independence, a radical reform of the education sector, the adoption of many laws regulating relations in the field of education, achieving quality and efficiency of education is the main goal of the national education system of any state. The state is analyzed, and this process is a highly continuous development of the material and technical base of educational institutions, improvement of its regulatory framework, educational and methodological support, modernization of management and control of education based on modern pedagogical technologies.

Keywords: Innovative approach, labor market, development, education, science, social development, higher education, development of personality and society, reform, intellectual development, socio-economic development, non-governmental educational institutions.

Introduction. Since the first years of independence, the development of the education system in our country has been elevated to the level of state policy, and effective work has been carried out to ensure that our youth acquire modern knowledge and professions in conditions that meet world standards, mature into physically and spiritually mature people, realize their abilities, talents, and intellectual potential, and cultivate in their hearts a sense of loyalty and selflessness to our homeland.

As you know, the "Strategy of Actions in Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021" was approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev's Decree No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" and Resolutions No. PQ-2752 dated June 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher educational institutions and ensure their active participation in the comprehensive reforms being implemented in the country" and No. PQ-4391 dated July 11, 2019 "On measures to introduce new principles of management in the system of higher and secondary specialized education", Resolution No. 967 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 3, 2019 "On the gradual transition of higher educational institutions to self-financing", Decree No. 133-f of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 25, 2019 serves as the basis for a fundamental reform of today's higher education system.

Indeed, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" of February 7, 2017, sets out a number of priority tasks for the development of the social sphere, in particular, education and science. This adopted document provides for strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions, the construction, repair and overhaul of new educational institutions, as well as providing them with modern educational and laboratory equipment, computer equipment

and teaching aids. Based on the Action Strategy, a number of decrees and resolutions were adopted aimed at further improving the personnel training system in our country, providing the economic and social sectors with highly qualified specialists, taking into account the current and future needs of employers in the training of bachelors and masters and achieving the harmony of educational areas, introducing medium-term target programs for structural changes in the economy, modernization, technical and technological re-equipment and diversification of industries, and comprehensive socio-economic development of regions.

Research methodology. Today, in the era of high technology and informatization processes in the world, the competition between companies for the training of highly qualified specialists has increased somewhat. This applies not only to commercial organizations, but also to scientific research centers and educational institutions. Indeed, the issue of the quality of modern education is one of the problems that must be solved first of all. After all, the higher educational institutions existing in our country form the knowledge of specialists in a specific professional field in the future.

Today, education has become the highest priority of state policy. During the years of independence, the composition of state budget expenditures has changed qualitatively. Currently, the main place in state expenditures is occupied by financing the implementation of a strong social policy and social protection of the population. The funds allocated from the state budget for education are planned at the level of 33.7 percent of budget expenditures, and the volume of expenditures directed to the education sector is 10-12 percent of the GDP of our country.

The education system is important in the implementation of social policy for three main reasons. These are:

- education is one of the main factors in the exercise of the right of people to follow the law and participate in building a democratic society;
- education ensures economic growth and provides people with the skills necessary to make a material contribution to the economy;
- education is considered an important part of social wealth, which plays a fundamental role in restoring the rich intellectual and national heritage of the Uzbek people.

Education is an investment in the human factor. Society as a whole is interested in it. After all, improving the level and quality of education ensures economic growth, increases labor productivity, finds rational solutions to social problems, and ultimately determines the country's place in the international community.

In order to solve existing economic problems in the conditions of strong international competition, it is necessary to ensure the full and effective use of the intellectual potential of the population. One of the main principles of state policy in the field of education is to be educated and encourage talent; to harmonize state and public management in the education system, and to have a humane, democratic character of education and upbringing. Knowledge, as a product of the educational sphere, has its own characteristics: it is a priceless social benefit; it is unlimited and does not decrease with use; it is not dependent on space; it is not refundable; the value it creates does not depend on the intensity of its subsequent use; it is time-related, etc.

Achieving the quality and efficiency of education is the main goal of the national education system of any state, and this process requires the continuous development of the material and technical base of higher education institutions, the improvement of their regulatory and legal framework, the modernization of educational and methodological support, education management and control based on modern pedagogical technologies, the organization of the personnel training system in accordance with the needs of the world, society, customer enterprises and organizations, and the improvement of the educational content of the system of retraining and advanced training of teachers of the higher education system based on foreign experience.

Nowadays, while the attention to the introduction of innovative pedagogical and information technologies in the education system is increasing, improving the content and quality of education is unimaginable today without a new direction of pedagogical innovation. The introduction of innovative processes and innovative innovations in the education system is determined by the professional capabilities of the teacher. In particular, the role and importance of modern teaching methods, interactive methods, and innovative technologies in teaching the subject of the world education system are incomparable.

Conclusion. Thus, a new education system is being established in our country, aimed at entering the global educational arena. Simultaneously with this process, significant changes are taking place in the theory and practice of the pedagogical educational process. The structure of approaches in education is changing, and different attitudes and pedagogical mentalities are being established. The education system is being enriched by the ability to work with new information, focusing on the individualization of the educational program, creative solutions. In the process of teaching innovative technologies in higher educational institutions, a factor remains the training of highly qualified personnel, the formation of their professional competence, improving their methodological skills, and equipping them with modern technologies.

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